

Performance Degradation and Protective Effects of Atomic Layer Deposition for Mg-based Thermoelectric Modules

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Thermoelectric technology has witnessed a resurgence in recent years due to increasing demands for sustainable energy sources and efficient cooling systems. Recently, the introduction of Te-free thermoelectric modules using non-toxic, abundant materials including *p*-type MgAgSb and *n*-type Mg₃(Sb,Bi)₂ marked a significant breakthrough. Despite promising performance, questions persist regarding long-term robustness and stability, especially in harsh environments. In this study, a thorough exploration of thermoelectric modules is conducted, focusing on their performance degradation under various conditions. Through elemental mapping analysis, degradation mechanisms are identified within the modules during cycling in argon environments, where atomic migrations and the formation of complex oxides at contact regions are key factors. Furthermore, cycling tests in air reveal significant degradation, prompting the exploration of protective strategies. Surface coatings using atomic layer deposition (ALD) emerge as a promising solution, particularly by HfO₂, demonstrating superior protective effects. Furthermore, re-soldering effectively restores module performance is found, highlighting the importance of developing advanced soldering techniques to promote magnesium-based thermoelectric technology as a sustainable alternative to Bi₂Te₃. These findings emphasize the importance of exploring novel contact materials and demonstrate the potential of ALD as a universal approach to enhancing module reliability and robustness.

which has a history spanning two centuries, has recently experienced a resurgence in research and development efforts. Operating on the principle of harnessing the coupled flow of electrical current and heat using solid-state materials, thermoelectric technology shows promise in both converting waste heat into electrical energy and providing localized cooling solutions. It offers unique advantages, including noiseless operation, minimal maintenance requirements, and exceptional reliability. Notably, applications of thermoelectric technology near room temperature constitute the largest and fastest-growing segment of the future thermoelectric market.^[1] This encompasses various applications such as cryotherapy, telecommunication, biomedicine, self-powered sensors for the *Internet of Things*, and waste heat recovery from sources like geothermal energy.^[2] The realization of these applications hinges on advancements in high-performance thermoelectric materials and their successful translation into advanced modules and devices.^[3]

Historically, thermoelectric applications have been dominated by Bi₂Te₃-based modules, primarily due to their unmatched performance near room temperature. However, the presence of tellurium (Te) in Bi₂Te₃, a toxic and extremely scarce element found in concentrations of <0.001 ppm in the Earth's crust, raises concerns about its

1. Introduction

In response to the growing demand for sustainable energy sources and efficient cooling systems, thermoelectric technology,

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sustainability.^[4] Progress in finding sustainable materials stagnated for over half a century until the recent material revolution, featuring notable successes including *n*-type Mg₃(Sb,Bi)₂ and *p*-type MgAgSb, which exhibited performance comparable to Bi₂Te₃-based materials.^[5] In 2021, building on the great success of materials development, a breakthrough was achieved by us, shattering the Bi₂Te₃ monopoly with the creation of the first Te-free thermoelectric modules utilizing the aforementioned Mg-based materials. The high performance of these modules renders them suitable for near-room temperature applications.^[6] Subsequent research, using similar or different materials such as *n*-type Mg₂(Si,Sn), has demonstrated that Te-free modules can match or even surpass the performance of Bi₂Te₃, significantly advancing the feasibility of non-toxic, sustainable thermoelectric technology.^[7]

Despite the successful demonstration of module-level performance with Mg-based technology, lots of questions remain regarding the evaluation of modules under various working conditions and the long-term robustness and operational stability of these modules.^[8] Particularly, the stability and long-term performance of thermoelectric modules are of paramount importance, especially considering their usage in harsh environments. The complex interplay of chemical, thermal, and mechanical factors can potentially lead to module degradation and failure. Moreover, the emphasis on long-term reliability is particularly pertinent as thermoelectric technology is expected to function without the need for maintenance in various applications, including space missions and nuclear reactors. Surprisingly, the commercial Bi₂Te₃ modules, which have been the only choice for near-room-temperature applications for several decades, exhibit unsatisfactory cycling stability, with efficiency degrading by 10% to 15% after only 6000 cycles.^[9] While the thermal stabilities of thermoelectric technology have garnered increased attention in recent years, a tentative testing protocol was only recently suggested by Jørgensen and Iversen.^[10] Moreover, many thermal stability studies, whether involving thermal cycling or aging, typically conducted tests for a limited duration—ranging from several hours to a few hundred hours.^[11] Those testing results are valuable but might be inadequate, considering the expectation that thermoelectric modules should function seamlessly for months to years without degradation. To address this gap, our prior research demonstrated the superior cycling performance of Mg-based modules, showcasing a degradation of <10% in output power after over 32 000 cycles (equivalent to 7 months).^[12] This highlighted a substantial advantage over the current state-of-the-art Bi₂Te₃ modules. Nonetheless, our previous cycling tests had limitations, as they were conducted in an argon-protected environment with oxygen content maintained below 1 ppm, which fails to replicate real-world conditions fully.

Based on the cumulative findings from previous research, two pivotal questions emerge: 1) What are the intrinsic degradation mechanisms of Mg-based modules during cycling in argon? and 2) Can we preserve cycling performance when modules are subjected to air? The answer to the first question pertains to the “inherent” degradation mechanisms, while the second question addresses “external” factors influencing degradation. To address the first question, note that previous studies have revealed that the primary cause of degradation in such modules stems from the contact regions, particularly at the hot side.^[7e,9a,b,13] There-

Figure 1. A schematic of the atomic layer deposition principle and its protective power for thermoelectric modules.

fore, these hot-side contact regions require special attention to understand the “inherent” degradation mechanisms. Accordingly, we conducted elemental mapping analysis using energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX) in a scanning electron microscope (SEM) for contact regions between MgAgSb/Ag and Mg₃(Sb,Bi)₂/Fe that were either uncycled or cycled for >40 000 cycles in argon. Our findings indicate that the “inherent” degradation of modules after cycling is attributed to atomic migrations, particularly the accumulation of oxygen at the interface regions. Additionally, the formation and rapid expansion of an Ag₃Sb layer at the MgAgSb/Ag interface underscore the need to replace Ag as the contact material.

For the second question concerning the “external” degrading factors, we ran the same cycling tests in the air. We observed significant degradation after only 5000 cycles. The accelerated performance loss was due to the degradation of the solder material. This degradation resulted from a thermochemical factor due to heating and oxygen exposure. These results highlight the need for additional measures to ensure the applicability of Mg-based technology. To address this, we applied surface coatings for protection using atomic layer deposition (ALD). ALD is based on surface-limited chemical reactions and leads to conform coating of the 3D structure of the thermoelectric module. In comparison to alternative passivation technologies like boron nitride (BN) spraying,^[14] ALD offers unique advantages:^[15] 1) ALD enables precise control over coating thickness due to its self-limiting half-cycle-reaction nature, allowing thickness regulation down to the sub-nanometer scale. 2) Unlike BN spraying, ALD coatings achieve high density, ensuring comprehensive coverage—a crucial factor for effective protection. 3) ALD’s non-line-of-sight capability ensures uniform coating on all surfaces, regardless of orientation relative to the coating material source.

These features are particularly advantageous for thermoelectric modules with complex topologies, where traditional techniques like BN spraying struggle to coat surfaces at the back side and the interior, rendering them unsuitable for such applications. We coated HfO₂ that is mature in ALD processing for a thickness of 300 nm. The schematic of this concept is shown in **Figure 1**. The coating strategy shows excellent protective effects by impeding the increase in internal resistance. Our work has not only revealed the dynamics of atomic diffusion under repeated

thermal input but has also showcased the significant potential of ALD as a universal approach to enhance the reliability and robustness of thermoelectric modules. These results further validate the application potential of Mg-based technology as a sustainable replacement for Bi₂Te₃-based solutions in the near future with improved sustainability and higher performance.

2. Results and Discussion

2.1. Atomic Diffusion at the Contact Interface

To uncover the underlying degradation mechanisms “inherent” to the modules, we investigate the interface regions between the *n*-type Mg_{3.3}Bi_{1.29}Sb_{0.7}Te_{0.01} (simplified as Mg₃(Sb,Bi)₂) and iron (Fe) by using a scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and energy-dispersive X-ray (EDX) mapping. The elemental composition presented in the maps encompasses magnesium (Mg), antimony (Sb), iron (Fe), and oxygen (O), with the omission of bismuth (Bi) for conciseness. Two specimens were examined: one designated as “Pre-cycling”, representing the as-sintered sample, and the other, designated as “Post-cycling” maintained within an argon-protected glovebox, subjected to thermal cycling between 100 and 250 °C for over 40 000 times. Detailed information regarding the cycling conditions is available in the Experimental Section.

The secondary electron image reveals that, while the interface exhibits well-defined boundaries, the presence of μm-sized Mg₃(Sb,Bi)₂ particles within the Fe component can be found before cycling. Furthermore, from the elemental line scan data provided in Figure S1 (Supporting Information), we observe a transition region between the contact and the thermoelectric materials that span ≈4 μm before cycling. It is evident that magnesium exhibits a degree of enrichment at the interface together with an enrichment of oxygen, strongly indicating the presence of magnesium oxide (MgO). Further examination reveals that oxygen enrichment predominantly resides on the Fe side. This distribution of MgO and Mg₃(Sb,Bi)₂ can be attributed to the sintering process, wherein the thermoelectric material undergoes sintering first and infiltrates into interstices between Fe particles before the sintering of the latter, ultimately leading to the distribution of these MgO and Mg₃(Sb,Bi)₂ particles into the Fe side. (Figure 2)

After cycling, the interface region undergoes significant alterations. As observed in the secondary electron image, a new interface region is formed with dark grain boundaries (GB). This region infiltrates into the thermoelectric material by 50 to 80 μm. Elemental maps reveal that the dark GB corresponds to the accumulation of MgO. Comparing the two oxygen maps, we observe an oxygen-rich-zone variation from the iron side (as-sintered) to the Mg₃(Sb,Bi)₂ side (post-cycled). This finding is particularly intriguing, as it suggests that MgO diffuses along grain boundaries in response to the applied thermal gradient. This diffusion phenomenon hints at the performance degradation of the modules, as MgO impurity phases transform from discrete “particles” into a continuous covering along the thermoelectric grains, thereby exacerbating electron impediments at grain boundaries. Furthermore, the migration of MgO along grain boundaries contributes to a degradation of mechanical properties due to its large mismatch of the coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE, ≈30 to 40 ppm K⁻¹ for MgO)^[16] with the thermoelectric mate-

Figure 2. Secondary electron images and energy-dispersive X-ray (EDX) maps taken in the SEM depicting the interface region between the *n*-type Mg_{3.3}Bi_{1.29}Sb_{0.7}Te_{0.01} and iron (Fe) of (Upper) the as-sintered and (Lower) the cycled specimen. The cycling was conducted in an Ar-protected environment for <40 000 times. The scale bars represent 20 μm. The white-dashed circle highlights the contrast change of grain boundaries after cycling. Note that the data were taken at different regions of the sample.

rials (≈20 ppm K⁻¹ for MgAgSb and Mg₃(Sb,Bi)₂),^[17] Moreover, MgO reacts easily with humidity to form Mg(OH)₂, rendering the long-term performance of the thermoelectric device vulnerable.

To understand the formation of MgO, we show, in Table 1, the thermodynamic data (i.e., standard molar Gibbs energy of formation at 298.15 K) of MgO and Fe binary oxides.^[18] The oxidation at the contact zone can be explained in the first instance by calculating the standard reaction Gibbs energy (Δ_rG°) of the Fe binary oxides presumably present in the Fe powder contact layer with pure Mg.

The negative values of Δ_rG° indicate these reactions are thermodynamically possible and Mg will react with the iron oxide of the Fe-contact layer, reducing the iron oxides and producing MgO, in agreement with the oxygen mapping results.

Table 1. Standard molar Gibbs energy of formation for MgO and Fe binary oxides at 298.15 K.

Compounds	MgO	Fe ₃ O ₄	Fe ₂ O ₃	FeO
Δ _r G° kJ mol ⁻¹	-569.3	-1015.4	-742.2	-251.4
Δ _r G° (kJ mol ⁻¹)				

Figure 3. Secondary electron images and energy-dispersive X-ray (EDX) mapping depicting the interface region between MgAgSb and Silver (Ag) of (Upper) the as-sintered and (Lower) the cycled specimen. The cycling was conducted in an Ar-protected environment for <40 000 times. The scale bar represents 10 μm .

To address the challenge posed by MgO migration within the *n*-type leg, it is advisable to employ higher-purity elements for thermoelectric material preparation and consider the replacement of Fe powder as a contact material, given its susceptibility to oxidation. Recent studies have demonstrated successful replacements such as Fe foil, stainless steels, and various metallic alloys, which offer promising avenues for enhancing contact design, aligning with research endeavors analogous to our investigation.^[13d,19]

In **Figure 3**, we present secondary electron images and EDX maps of interfaces between *p*-type $\text{MgAg}_{0.965}\text{Ni}_{0.005}\text{Sb}_{0.99}$ (simplified as MgAgSb) and Ag, both before and after undergoing <40 000 thermal cycles. The pre-cycling secondary electron image reveals a distinct and well-defined interface between MgAgSb and Ag. The elemental line-scan profiles in **Figure S2** (Supporting Information) confirm that the transition region spans only 4 μm . Furthermore, the EDX map indicates a slightly higher oxygen concentration on the thermoelectric side compared to the Ag side, likely attributed to the greater affinity of Mg to oxidation.

Following the thermal cycling, the interface region becomes considerably broader, mirroring the behavior observed in the *n*-type leg. An evident increase in oxygen concentration is observed, accumulating in a linear pattern along the boundaries between the thermoelectric material and the contact material. Furthermore, the interface exhibits a “coral”-like structure, comprised of a mixture of Mg, Ag, O, and Sb. A magnified image of such a “coral”-like structure is shown in **Figure S3** (Supporting Information). Furthermore, elemental distribution maps for Ag and Sb reveal discernible patterns. As illustrated in **Figure 3**, both Ag and Sb display an intermediate region located between the initial Ag-contact layer and the thermoelectric materials, spanning ap-

proximately ≈ 20 to 40 μm , as indicated by the dash lines in both maps. The quantitative analysis unveils a rough ratio of 3:1, signifying the formation of the Ag_3Sb layer during thermal cycling, as shown in **Figure S4** (Supporting Information). Although the formation of Ag_3Sb at the interface has been recorded,^[12] it is crucial to fathom the underlying dynamics governing Ag_3Sb formation and to discern whether Ag migrates toward Sb, or Sb migrates toward Ag. This distinction becomes evident upon scrutiny of the curvature of the intermediate region, which notably “curves toward” the Ag-dominant side, providing compelling evidence of Sb atoms migrating toward Ag. The spatial distribution of Ag_3Sb within the intermediate region further strengthens the inference of Sb atoms migrating toward Ag, as this region predominantly resides within the Ag-rich side. It is noteworthy that this migration of Sb must overcome the diffusive forces induced by the thermal gradient, given the higher temperature on the Ag side.

Our investigation underscores that Ag possesses the intrinsic capability to robustly “attract” Sb atoms from the MgAgSb material, thereby facilitating the genesis of Ag_3Sb . Consequently, it can be deduced that Ag is not an optimal choice for contact material, not only for MgAgSb but potentially for other materials where Sb is a significant constituent, such as skutterudites or Sb-based half-Heuslers. Moreover, in line with the extensive discussions in the existing literature, the emergence of Ag_3Sb exerts a deleterious influence on thermoelectric performance, leading to a discernible degradation of the Seebeck coefficient and an elevation in thermal conductivity.^[5a,b,20] This implies that any residual unreacted Ag particles within MgAgSb will progressively undermine thermoelectric performance by actively promoting the formation of Ag_3Sb . Consequently, our findings underscore the pivotal significance of achieving high-performance MgAgSb thermoelectric materials through a concerted effort to minimize the presence of unreacted Ag, which is in alignment with established practices.^[20]

It is worth reiterating a pivotal observation from this study—the conspicuous accumulation of oxygen in the vicinity of the boundary region. Given that the entire cycling process was conducted within an argon-protected environment featuring an oxygen concentration of <1 ppm, the presence of oxygen at the interface necessitates its migration from the Fe powder forming the contact layer. Otherwise, oxide formation would manifest not only at contact regions but also deeper within the thermoelectric leg following cycling. This suggests that intrinsic oxygen contamination within the thermoelectric leg may underlie long-term property degradation. Sources of this oxygen may include the raw materials, as most commercial suppliers of metallic chemical elements do not calculate oxygen in their purity labels (i.e., the purities are labeled as “Metal Basis”). Alternatively, oxygen ingress during processing steps such as high-energy ball milling or sintering, where oxygen leakage is virtually unavoidable, can also lead to material oxidation. However, it should also be noted that oxygen content in contacting materials is often not reported in other works, making direct comparisons of purities across different studies challenging. Overall, our findings underscore the imperative of utilizing elements with low oxygen content and/or implementing cleaner processing conditions to minimize oxygen content when fabricating thermoelectric and contact materials based on $\text{Mg}_3(\text{Sb,Bi})_2$ and MgAgSb.

Figure 4. a) Variation of internal resistance (R_{in}) of modules upon thermal cycling. The images show the modules (b,c) before and (d,e) after cycling. Two modules are compared, either (b,d) without coating or (c,e) ALD-coated by HfO₂. The circles in (a) show the internal resistance of re-assembled modules by re-soldering the extracted thermoelectric legs from the post-cycled modules. The recording of R_{in} failed for the module cycled in Ar after $\approx 35\,000$ times due to the in-module circuit break.

2.2. Cycling Study of Modules in Air with ALD Coating

In parallel with the cycling of individual thermoelectric legs, we conducted cycling tests on complete thermoelectric modules comprising four legs. To assess the module's degradation, we continuously monitored the internal resistance (R_{in}) after each cycle. Furthermore, to enhance the modules' robustness against cycling in air, we employed ALD to hafnium oxide (HfO₂) protective coating to the modules. The selection of the material was based on its well-established and standardized processing within the ALD community, as well as its inherent stability in ambient air conditions.^[21] In total, three distinct conditions were employed for comparative assessment: 1) cycling within an argon-protected glovebox (labeled as "Ar"); 2) cycling in ambient air ("Air"); and 3) cycling in ambient air with HfO₂ coating via atomic layer deposition ("HfO₂"). The thickness of the coating materials was maintained at ≈ 300 nm. Throughout the cycling process, the cold side was held at a constant temperature of 20 °C, while the hot side experienced temperature variations between 100 and 250 °C with an average heating rate of 74 °C min⁻¹ and an average cooling rate of 58 °C min⁻¹. Comprehensive details about module fabrication, measurement procedures, cycling conditions, ALD growth conditions, and other relevant aspects are provided in the Experimental Section.

In **Figure 4a**, we present the cycling-number-dependent R_{in} for different modules. For clarity, we set the resistance cutoff at 0.8 Ohms, with a detailed view provided in **Figure S5** (Supporting Information). Additionally, we investigated the protective effect of alumina coating and recorded its R_{in} variation upon cycling in air in **Figure S5** (Supporting Information). However, due to its relatively weaker protective effects, alumina coating was not further analyzed in subsequent studies. The findings reveal that when the module underwent cycling in an argon environment, the R_{in} value remained relatively constant until a degradation occurred at $\approx 30\,000$ cycling times, resulting in a substantial increase in R_{in} . However, beyond cycling in argon, a more critical evaluation pertains to the performance of modules subjected to real environmental conditions, notably in the

air where oxygen and moisture are present. Consequently, we conducted similar cycling tests under identical heat profiles but within an ambient air environment. Regrettably, cycling the module in ambient air led to a significantly accelerated degradation, manifesting at ≈ 5000 cycling times, as also shown in **Figure 4a**. This outcome underscores the substantial deleterious impact of the ambient environment on the module's stability. The **Figure S6** (Supporting Information) provides additional insights into the environmental conditions, including relative humidity and temperature.

On the other hand, and intriguingly, the ALD coatings process revealed a substantial augmentation in the stability of modules when subjected to ambient air conditions even after extending the cycling duration to $\approx 65\,000$ times, in stark contrast to their non-coated counterparts that started degradation only after 5000 cycles. These findings incontrovertibly accentuate the efficacy of ALD coating as a safeguard mechanism for bolstering the thermal resilience of Mg-based thermoelectric modules. Further discussions concerning the variations of the resistance are provided in the Supporting Information.

These discoveries have sparked considerable interest in unraveling the degradation mechanisms of these modules. Initially, we explored the possibility of alterations in the thermoelectric materials. First, through SEM and EDX mapping, as shown in **Figures S7** and **S8** (Supporting Information), we examined the surfaces of both the *n*- and *p*-type thermoelectric materials. We also quantified the elements by using EDX for the *n*-type leg cycled in air without coating. The results, shown in **Table S1** (Supporting Information), suggest that the compositions are nearly identical on the hot side and the cold side, suggesting no occurrence of Mg loss, which differs from the observation in other works that usually apply a higher temperature heat treatment in a vacuum.^[22] However, our comparative analysis did not reveal any evident alterations on these surfaces following thermal cycling. Furthermore, we conducted a detailed assessment of the thermoelectric materials' performance, with the results presented in **Figure S9** (Supporting Information). Notably, we observed that the power factor of all materials consistently

exhibited similar values, and the overall performance demonstrated negligible variations across different cycling conditions.

Second, we conducted contact resistance measurements on the legs extracted from the module subjected to $\approx 65\,000$ cycles in an Ar environment. As shown in Figure S10 (Supporting Information), post-cycling, the contact resistivity values at the cold side are ≈ 8.8 and $29\ \mu\text{Ohm cm}^2$ for the *p*-type/Ag and *n*-type/Fe junctions, respectively. These values exhibit a minor increase compared to the pre-cycling values reported in our earlier study,^[6] where they were ≈ 6 and $26\ \mu\text{Ohm cm}^2$, respectively. This suggests that the cold side remains relatively unaffected by thermal cycling. However, there is a noticeable increase in the contact resistivity on the hot side, rising to ≈ 150 to $160\ \mu\text{Ohm cm}^2$ for both junctions. This points to significant microstructural evolution at play, contributing to the interface resistance.

Utilizing these updated contact resistance values, we conducted module-level simulations, revealing that the contact resistance enhancement led to approximately a 10% decrease in output power, consistent with experimental measurements on the module, as illustrated in Figure S11 (Supporting Information). The increased contact resistance is responsible for the degradation observed in the module after resoldering. Notably, although the loss in output power is discernible, its magnitude is not substantial. This can be attributed to our utilization of relatively long leg lengths, ≈ 8 mm in this study. Consequently, the contribution of contact resistance to the total R_{in} remains modest, resulting in marginal performance degradation. However, shortening the leg length to ≈ 2 mm or even shorter may become necessary in practical applications for purposes such as enhancing output power density or reducing material costs. Under such circumstances, the amplified contact resistance would significantly impair module performance. Hence, there is a pressing need to explore more resilient contact materials and methods resistant to heat treatment.

Furthermore, notably, the modules exhibit distinctive visual transformations following thermal cycling. Images of pre-cycling modules reveal their as-fabricated state (Figure 4b) or HfO₂-coated state (Figure 4c). The ALD coating imparts a purple-green coloration to the surfaces of the thermoelectric legs. After $\approx 20\,000$ thermal cycles, the uncoated modules (Figure 4d) undergo complete degradation, evident in the visual transformation where the Cu-electrodes on the hot (upper) side display a gray hue, in stark contrast to the ones on the cold (lower) side. Conversely, the Cu electrodes on both sides of the HfO₂-coated module exhibit minimal contrast (Figure 4e), indicative of a protective effect conferred by HfO₂. Notably, a sponge-like, fluffy material accumulates at the contact region when cycled in the air without coating (Figure 4d), appearing in both *n*- and *p*-type legs, and exclusively within the hot-side contact regions. In contrast, this fluffy material is absent in the module protected by HfO₂.

For a deepened understanding, we use SEM and EDX to examine the “fluffy” materials that appeared at the hot side junctions between thermoelectric legs and electrodes after cycling in the air. As shown in Figure S12 (Supporting Information), the secondary electron image reveals the porous structure of the fluffy materials, consistent with observations from optical images in Figure 4d. We further observe granular microstructures with a grain size of ≈ 500 nm. Further EDX analysis allows quantifying the elemental ratio of Pb/Sn/O, yielding values of 21/34/45, re-

spectively, as shown in Table S2 (Supporting Information). The substantial amount of oxygen suggests the formation of SnO and PbO. These observations lead us to hypothesize that it is the oxidized soldering materials that degraded the performance of the module.

To validate our conjecture, we extracted the thermoelectric legs from specific cycled modules and fabricated new modules by re-soldering the legs after cycling. Figure 4 also illustrates the R_{in} of newly assembled modules after re-soldering. Evidently, for modules cycled in argon and in the air with HfO₂ protection, the re-soldering process significantly reduces the R_{in} value, approaching that of the as-prepared, pre-cycling modules. For the unprotected module cycled in air, re-soldering could also reduce the R_{in} value significantly, but the recovery is comparatively insignificant despite a lower cycling number ($\approx 20\,000$ times). To further examine the effect of re-soldering, we measured and compared the output powers of these modules at different stages. Figure 5a demonstrates that the HfO₂-protected module and the in-argon-cycled module recover 93% and 95% relative output power, respectively, after $\approx 65\,000$ cycling times. In contrast, the air-cycled modules could only recover 64% of the relative output power if uncoated, despite a lower cycling number ($\approx 20\,000$ times). This evidence underscores that the soldering material between the thermoelectric leg and the electrical circuit constitutes the primary source of degradation in thermoelectric modules based on MgAgSb/Mg₃(Sb,Bi)₂. Note that it has been shown that the degradation of performance in Bi₂Te₃-based modules can be attributed to the formation of cracks between the thermoelectric leg and the solder. This mechanism bears similarity to the degradation observed in Mg-based modules to certain degrees. Therefore, the development of advanced solder materials and technologies is crucial for improving the cycling performance and overall stability of a broader range of modules.^[8a,9b] Our study thus underscores the critical importance of employing advanced brazing techniques endowed with superior thermal robustness against ambient conditions to ensure the long-term viability of thermoelectric technology.

To comprehensively assess the protective efficacy of the HfO₂ coating, we present a detailed analysis of the module performance of the HfO₂-coated module subjected to $\approx 65\,000$ cycles in an air environment, comparing it with an uncoated counterpart. Complete module characterization, including heat flow and efficiency, is available in Figure S13 (Supporting Information). However, to assess the impacts of cycling and surface coating more effectively, we focus solely on the electrical properties of the modules, as they are less susceptible to measurement uncertainties. In Figure 5b, we present the voltage-current (U-I) curves for the power generation modules. To avoid redundancy, a single ΔT was applied, with the hot side at 250 °C and the cold side at 25 °C. These U-I curves exhibit excellent linearity, enabling the determination of the module's internal resistance (R_{in}) and open-circuit voltage (V_{OC}) through slope and intercept calculations. Detailed results can be found in Table 2. The output power reveals a maximum corresponding to the matched impedance condition, where the internal resistance aligns with the load resistance.

Impressively, the module with the HfO₂ coating maintains $\approx 93\%$ of its relative output power after re-soldering, outperforming the uncoated module ($\approx 64\%$). This result underscores the exceptional robustness achieved through the HfO₂ surface

Figure 5. a) Variations of the relative output power of various modules (Black square: cycled in Ar. Red circle: cycled in Air without coating. Green pentagon: cycled in Air with HfO_2 protection) at different stages (pre-cycle, post-cycle, and re-solder). b) Comparisons of the Voltage-Current (U - I) curves and output power (P) between the in-air cycled modules without protection or with HfO_2 protection.

coating. Furthermore, it highlights the necessity of developing more advanced soldering materials and processes to further enhance the thermal robustness of Mg-based modules. Overall, the HfO_2 -coated module's performance not only substantiates the feasibility of Mg-based thermoelectric materials but also highlights the promising potential of surface coatings, offering enhanced durability and stability in real-world operating conditions. Our findings reinforce the efficacy of Mg-based technology as a viable replacement for Bi_2Te_3 in applications utilizing low-grade heat sources with temperatures below $300\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, particularly when considering sustainability and long-term reliability.

3. Conclusion

This study provides a thorough investigation into thermoelectric contacts and modules, focusing on the intricate interface regions between n -type $\text{Mg}_3(\text{Sb},\text{Bi})_2$ and Fe, as well as p -type MgAgSb and Ag. Through EDX analysis, we uncover elemental diffusion phenomena at these interfaces. Specifically, our findings reveal the accumulation of MgO at grain boundaries in the n -type interface, likely resulting from the diffusion of O impurities within $\text{Mg}_3(\text{Sb},\text{Bi})_2$. Conversely, in the p -type interface, the formation of Ag_3Sb between MgAgSb and Ag is observed. To mitigate such interdiffusion layers, we recommend assessing the oxygen content

of contact materials intended for use with Mg-based materials and exploring alternative contact materials.

Going beyond controlled laboratory environments, we investigate the real-condition impacts on thermoelectric modules through cycling tests in ambient air. The vulnerability of modules to air is evident, with a visible accumulation of oxidized soldering material at the hot-side contact region. Re-soldering experiments confirm its influence on module recovery, emphasizing the need for advanced brazing techniques for long-term viability. A groundbreaking protective strategy is introduced through ALD, particularly of HfO_2 . This coating proves remarkably effective in preserving module robustness, maintaining 93% of its relative output power after re-soldering, even after enduring $\approx 65\ 000$ cycles in air. The resulting module performance not only underscores the promise of Mg-based thermoelectric technology but also highlights the transformative potential of surface coatings in ensuring long-term reliability and efficiency. These insights illuminate a pathway toward sustainable, high-performance thermoelectric modules poised to revolutionize energy conversion and thermal management technologies. To advance this innovative realm and realize its profound implications for a more sustainable future, further exploration and optimization of contacting and coating materials and processes with thickness optimization, coupled with rigorous life cycle analysis, will be pivotal. This ongoing work is crucial for pushing the boundaries of

Table 2. Comparison of several key parameters of modules cycled in air with or without ALD-coated protective coating of HfO_2 . The cycling numbers are $\approx 20\ 000$ and $\approx 65\ 000$ for the uncoated and HfO_2 -coated modules, respectively.

$T_H = 250\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ $T_C = 25\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$	Air Pre-cycle	Air Post-cycle	Air Re-solder	HfO_2 Pre-cycle	HfO_2 Post-cycle	HfO_2 Re-solder
V_{OC} (V)	0.187	0.186	0.189	0.187	0.175	0.187
R_{in} (Ohm)	0.153	1.008	0.245	0.153	0.455	0.165
P_{max} (mW)	57.07	9.09	36.61	57.04	16.78	52.77
Relative P_{max} (%)	100	16	64	100	29	93

thermoelectric technology and achieving its full potential in contributing to a more sustainable energy landscape.

4. Experimental Section

Sample Preparation: The *n*-type $\text{Mg}_{3.3}\text{Bi}_{1.29}\text{Sb}_{0.7}\text{Te}_{0.01}$ and *p*-type $\text{MgAg}_{0.965}\text{Ni}_{0.005}\text{Sb}_{0.99}$ were prepared following a methodology outlined in the prior publications.^[6] High-purity Bi (99.9%), Sb (99.99%), Te (99.99%), Mg (99.8%), and Ag (99.9%) powders were precisely weighed according to stoichiometry. These elements were then loaded into a glove box, maintaining an argon atmosphere with oxygen and water levels below 1 ppm. Subsequently, the mixture was ball-milled using a SPEX 8000D machine. The resulting ball-milled powders, along with the respective contact powders (Ag for *p*-type and Fe (99.5%) for *n*-type), were loaded into a 20 mm inner diameter mold within a glove box and immediately sintered using a field-assisted sintering technique (FAST, FCT System GmbH). Note that the labeled purities of the raw elements are designated as “metal basis,” indicating that only metallic elements are accounted for in the purity calculation, while oxygen contents are not included and, therefore, unknown. To address this concern, both Fe and Ag powders used as contact materials were characterized for oxygen content using an inert gas fusion technique (LECO ONH 836 Analyzer). The characterization revealed oxygen contents of 0.30(2) mass% and 0.010(1) mass% in Fe and Ag powders, respectively. For *p*-type materials, sintering employed tungsten carbide (WC) tools under 120 MPa pressure at 280 °C for 3 min, while *n*-type materials were sintered using graphite tools under 50 MPa pressure at 750 °C for 3 min. The thermoelectric properties including the electrical conductivity, the Seebeck coefficient, and the thermal conductivity were measured using standard methods. The complete thermoelectric properties are shown in Figure S14 (Supporting Information).

Module Fabrication and Measurement: The sintered *n*- and *p*-type bulk samples, together with contact layers, were precision-cut into $2.0 \times 2.0 \times 8.125$ mm³ pieces using a diamond wire saw. These pieces were then bonded to electrodes on both hot and cold sides using Sn-based solder ($\text{Pb}_{40}\text{Sn}_{60}$). Simultaneously, the electrodes were bonded to ceramic pieces with silver paste. The entire module underwent a heat treatment in a tube furnace at 290 °C for 30 min to solder the legs and electrodes. Copper wires were soldered onto the cold-side electrodes for 4-point current and voltage measurements. Evaluation of module performance was conducted using a Mini PEM (Advance Riko). The electrical output power (*P*) and output heat flow were measured under vacuum ($< 5 \times 10^{-2}$ mbar). A 0.1 mm graphite sheet and thermal silicone grease (ST1002, Slont) were employed between the ceramic plate and the heater to minimize thermal contact resistance. Good thermal contact was ensured using 60N compression springs. The hot-side temperature (T_{hot}) is 250 °C, while the cold-side temperature (T_{cold}) remained ≈ 25 °C.

The thermoelectric legs after thermal cycling were extracted inside an Ar-protected glovebox by melting the solder layers using a hot plate. The extracted legs were resoldered to fabricate new modules. The resoldering process involves three types of interfaces: 1) between the Cu electrodes and the ceramics; 2) between the Cu electrodes and the legs; and 3) between the cold-side electrodes and copper wires. It is important to note that for (1) and (2), they undergo a single-step preparation in a tube furnace at 290 °C for 30 min to “solder” the legs, electrodes, and ceramics. As for the Cu wires in (3), they are soldered separately after taking out the module from the tube furnace.

Thermal Cycling Tests: Thermal cycling of the thermoelectric legs, for both *n*- and *p*-type materials and their corresponding contact layers, was conducted within an argon-filled glove box using a custom-made setup. One side of the legs underwent heating from 100 to 250 °C, while the other side was cooled by a 20 °C heat sink. The internal resistance (R_{in}) of the thermoelectric module was evaluated through four-wire measurements after each cycle at a hot side temperature of 100 °C. Each heat cycle lasted ≈ 6 min. It is noteworthy that the new cycling temperature profile is more rigorous than this previous work due to higher temperatures and rapid alternations, creating a robust thermal shock testing condition.^[10]

Similarly, thermal cycling was performed on four modules using the same temperature profiles. Before cycling, the modules underwent initial measurements with the Mini-PEM to ensure consistent and optimal performance. One module was cycled in an argon-filled glove box, while the remaining three were cycled in air. Among the air-cycled modules, two were coated with protective oxide layers using atomic layer deposition (ALD) with either Al_2O_3 or HfO_2 . Further details on ALD conditions will be discussed in the following section.

Atomic Layer Deposition: The Al_2O_3 and HfO_2 protective coatings were deposited within a thermal ALD reactor (Veeco Savannah S200) at a controlled deposition temperature of 150 °C. Trimethylaluminum (TMA 97%, Sigma–Aldrich) and Tetrakis(dimethylamido) hafnium (IV) (TDMAH ≥ 99.99 , Sigma–Aldrich) served as the aluminum and hafnium precursors, respectively, with H_2O chosen as the oxidizer. Throughout the ALD process, TMA and H_2O were maintained at room temperature, while TDMAH was heated to 75 °C. A high-purity nitrogen flow of 20 sccm (99.999%) acted as both a carrier and purging gas. The optimal pulse and purge durations for one ALD deposition cycle of TMA/purge/ H_2O /purge and TDMAH/purge/ H_2O /purge were determined to be 0.1/15/0.015/20 s and 0.5/15/0.015/20 s, respectively.

Based on meticulous preliminary ALD experiments, growth per cycle (GPC) rates of 0.13 and 0.11 Å/cycle were achieved for Al_2O_3 and HfO_2 , respectively. Consequently, the ALD cycle numbers were adjusted to deposit ≈ 300 nm of Al_2O_3 and HfO_2 protective layers. It is worth noting that 20 pulses of TMA and TDMAH were employed to saturate the module surfaces with the respective precursor molecules.

Microstructural Characterization for Contact Interfaces: To achieve high-quality images, a superior surface is imperative. To ensure this, metallographic preparations had been applied to both pre-cycled and post-cycled legs. The polishing commences with coarse sandpaper featuring a grid number of P800 and progresses through finer ones, culminating in sandpaper with a grid number of P4000. Subsequently, diamond paper with a particle size of 0.5 μm was used to obtain fine polishing. It is crucial to note that, given the materials' sensitivity, especially the *n*-type $\text{Mg}_3(\text{Sb,Bi})_2$, to water, the entire polishing process must be conducted free of water. Thus, only high-purity, dry ethanol had been used during the polishing process. Following the fine polishing of the surfaces, the contact regions of both material types and their respective contact layers underwent characterization using energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX), as integrated within a ZEISS sigma scanning electron microscopy (SEM) device operated at 15 kV and with a working distance of 8 mm.

Supporting Information

Supporting Information is available from the Wiley Online Library or from the author.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

Keywords

atomic layer deposition, Mg-based module, sustainability, thermal cycling, thermoelectric modules

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